

NLR9672, Madhu, Vaigai, IET1722, TKM9, Kanchi, Rasi, Kannagi, ADT36, ADT31, TKM8, IR8, TNI, IR5, Co 25, Bhavani, Ponni, BCPI, and IR20. Other serious diseases include blast (Bl) and brown spot (BS).

Once minor diseases, bacterial blight (BB), sheath blight (ShB), sheath rot (ShR), and grain discoloration (Gld) are increasingly destructive and are beginning to affect almost all rice growing areas. False smut, bacterial leaf streak (BLS), stem rot, leaf scald,

udbatta, narrow brown leaf spot, and grassy stunt virus diseases also are increasing.

BB infection has been moderate to severe (3-7) in many states (see table) since 1980, and occurred in epidemic proportions in almost all of the Punjab in 1980 and 1981 kharif. Losses generally were 15-20% and sometimes rose to 40%. IR8, Jaya, and PR106, which are widely grown were highly susceptible.

BLS occurs widely but was worst in

Andhra Pradesh and the Punjab in 1980. Bl is common (see table) and attacks Jaya, Ratna, Basmati, Surekha, Mahsuri, Gurmatia, Phalguna, Kranti, IR8, and PR106. BS is a problem in upland and low fertility soils. ShR and Gl attack almost all high yielding varieties, including Phalguna, Surekha, Bangoli, PR106, IR8, Jaya, Co 40, Kranti, Ratna, and Mahsuri. However, Basmati, Mahsuri, Usha, Asha, and Pankaj varieties proved tolerant. *ℓ*

Recovery of virus from tungro (RTV)-infected leaves with or without leafhopper infestation

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Six-week-old TNI seedlings were caged with green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* that had fed on RTV-infected plants. RTV symptoms developed 2 wk after inoculation. Two or three new leaves were yellow or twisted, but the older leaves remained green and apparently healthy. Leaves with and without symptoms were taken from the infected plants and separately confined in test tubes for 1 d with new adult GLH. The GLH then were allowed individual 1-d inoculation access on 7d-old TNI seedlings. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in pots and percent seedling infection was recorded in 2 wk.

GLH recovery of virus from leaves of TNI plants infected with RTV at 2 stages, IRRI, 1985.

Leaf position	Insects		
	Tested (no.)	With virus (no.)	With virus (%)
<i>6 wk after soaking</i>			
1st youngest	20	19	95
2d	17	12	71
3d	20	10	50
4th	—	—	—
<i>2-leaf stage</i>			
1st youngest	40	37	93
2d	40	35	88
3d	39	7	18
4th	40	5	13

All the GLH recovered virus from leaves with symptoms and 57% of GLH recovered virus from the older leaves without symptoms. GLH recovery of RTV was highest from younger leaves

(see table). Leaves also were collected from plants inoculated at second-leaf stage 1 mo after inoculation. Virus recovery was also highest from younger leaves (see table).

A method for producing *Rhizoctonia solani* inoculum for field inoculation

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Artificial inoculation is necessary for studying sheath blight (ShB) caused by *R. solani*. Growing the fungal colony on potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates and inoculation by placing agar blocks in leaf sheaths works well for laboratory and greenhouse studies, but is cumbersome in the field. We sought to develop more suitable methods of inoculum production for field studies.

Table 1. Growth of *R. solani* on different media, Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Medium	Colony diameter ^a (mm)			
	After 24 h	After 48 h	After 72 h	After 96 h
Chaff	11.3	35.5	84.0	84.3
Straw	10.0	26.0	33.0	68.3
WA	33.0	57.5	86.0	86.0 ^b
Husk	8.6	16.0	74.6	84.0
Sawdust	7.3	11.3	12.6	13.8
Grain	16.6	86.0	86.0 ^b	86.0 ^b
Chaff + grain	14.3	37.6	84.0 ^b	84.0 ^b
PDA	25.5	85.0	85.0 ^b	85.0 ^b
Agar + chaff	12.3	36.6	84.0	84.0
Rice dust	7.6	57.3	83.3	84.0

^a Av of 3 replications. ^b Started to produce sclerotia.

Table 2. Effect of different media on *R. solani* sclerotia production, Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Medium	Mycelial growth	Sclerotial initiation ^a	Sclerotial produced ^b (no.)
Chaff	Fast	10	94.3
Straw	Moderate	24	93
WA	Very fast	4	20.3
Husk	Moderate	6	17.6
Sawdust	Slow	3	7
Grain	Very fast	3	3000
Chaff + grain	Fast	3	490
PDA	Very fast	3	65.6
Agar + chaff	Fast	4	143.6
Rice dust	Fast	4	39.6

^a In days after inoculation. ^b Av of 3 replications.

We tested rice chaff, straw, dust, husk, and grain and sawdust for growing *R. solani*. Five grams of each medium and 15 ml of distilled water were placed in petri dishes and autoclaved at 15 psi at 121°C for 15 min. These plates and plates of PDA and water agar (WA) were inoculated with one fast-growing *R. solani* sclerotium, placed in the center of the dish. Colony growth was measured by surface diameter.

The same media were tested in 250-ml flasks by mixing 15 g of raw materials and 45 ml distilled water and autoclaving as before. One *R. solani* sclerotium was the inoculant and sclerotia were counted after 30 d. PDA and WA were used as checks. Each of the following media was